

AT A GLANCE

Environments connected to Arctic fjords are changing rapidly, with consequences for society. A warmer climate is an important driver of change, but other factors also play a major role, including pressures and opportunities from fishing, tourism, shipping, and changing socio-economic conditions. FACE-IT is an EU-funded research program about managing the consequences of these changes with focus on marine biodiversity and Arctic societies.

A major activity in FACE-IT is to learn together with local communities about the relationship between environmental changes and Arctic livelihoods in order to support management at the local and national levels. The overarching objective of FACE-IT is to enable adaptive co-management of social-ecological fjord systems.

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Photo: Front: Porsangerfjorden. Photo: T. E. Mathisen, page 2: Svalbard. Photo: G. K. Hovelsrud, page 4: Ilulissat. Photo: A. Nilsson

THE FUTURE OF ARCTIC COASTAL ECOSYSTEMS

LEARNING TO MANAGE CHANGING FJORDS

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FJORD ECOSYSTEMS AND BIODIVERSITY

The future of ecosystems in Arctic fjord is closely linked to sea ice and the glaciers that are connected to the fjord. When the climate gets warmer, the environment in the water of the fjords will change, which in turn affects animals and people who depend on marine life. A core task in FACE-IT is to study the potential impact of climate change on the marine food web, including species that are important for coastal livelihoods and Indigenous people, such as fish, crustaceans, seabirds, and sea-mammals

LEARNING TOGETHER

The ambition of FACE-IT is that scientists and people in local communities work together to create knowledge for managing sustainable nature-based livelihoods and for adapting to the rapid changes in the Arctic.

The process of FACE-IT is designed as recurring interactions between local communities and the researchers in the project. Local activities includes site visits, interviews, and two workshops. The project also includes dialogues with policy makers at the local, national, and EU levels.

NATURE-BASED TOURISM

Arctic fjords have become tourist attractions with growing number of visitors. FACE-IT will study how the increased tourism activities in the coastal zone interlink with environmental changes in ways that may affect biodiversity, including wildlife. The goal is to develop a framework for assessing the local sustainability of tourism activities.

2021

Scoping visits:
Ilulissat, Svalbard,
Porsanger

Project design
EU funding
Horizon 2020

2022

Local interviews and
workshop to identify
locally relevant drivers
of change

Identify local
stakeholders and
concerns. Refine
local project aim

Analysis of local
input to develop
a first outlook of
different potential
futures

Local interviews
to refine narratives of
potential futures

Analysis of local
input together with
insights from studies
of changes in the
environment and
biodiversity

2023

Local workshop to
assess management
options

Synthesis of project
insights locally and
across field sites

2024

Outreach and closing
policy dialogue
meeting

FOOD PROVISION & LIVELIHOODS

Local livelihoods often depend on biodiversity and ecosystems that provide households with food, income, and a connection with culture and the environment. Small-scale business development and entrepreneurship also play an important role in community wellbeing.

As part of the fieldwork in communities, FACE-IT will assess how ecosystem-based livelihoods, such as fisheries, may be affected by environmental, societal and resource management changes. We will pay special attention to the role of gender, age, and culture in livelihood activities. FACE-IT will also analyse how changes in human activities might affect the environment in Arctic fjords